

EXTERNAL PARAMETERS OF YOUNG ANGUS CATTLE**Assistant - G. Eshmuratova****Scientific supervisor - M. Dosmuhammedova**

*Samarkand State Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry and Biotechnology
University, Nukus branch*

Abstract. The article presents information about the changes in the main body dimensions of bulls belonging to the Angus breed in the age section.

Keywords. *Index, exterior, bone density, productivity, body dimensions.*

Introduction. Cattle breeding is an important branch of animal husbandry. Cattle breeding plays a key role in maintaining the food security of the population, because almost all of the milk consumed by the population in our country, and about 70% of the meat, is obtained from cattle. It should be noted that beef is obtained mainly from dairy breeds and hybrid animals of different genotypes obtained as a result of their crossbreeding. It is known that the productivity of meat is directly related to the growth and development of animals. Therefore, the study and analysis of the data on the external indicators of young animals analyzed in the article determine the relevance of the topic. The climatic conditions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan are characterized by extreme variability. In the summer months, the climate is very hot and the solar radiation is strong, while in the winter, some days are very cold and the humidity is high.

Material and methods. In the conditions of Shukrullo Bobojonov and Shukhrat Bobojonov farms belonging to the Beruni district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, 30 calves of similar genetic origin, sex, and age were separated,

tied and untied, and 15 calves were fed to the I-control group. Angus male calves, 15 male calves of this breed were also selected for the II-experimental group.

Obtained results and their analysis. According to the purpose of the experiment, we took body measurements such as height at withers, height of withers, depth of chest, width and girth, width of iliac bones, oblique length of the body, girth of the leg from 6 and 18-month-old cattle and listed them in Table 1.

Table 1.

Changes in the main body size of the animals in the experimental groups in the age section, cm

Indicators	Groups			
	I		II	
	Age in months			
	6	18	6	18
The height of the rain	102,3±0,3	141,5±0,9	109,2±0,7	146,1±0,9
The height of the mound	104,1±0,9	142,5±0,1	112,5±0,9	148,2±0,4
Chest depth	54,1±0,4	88,3±0,5	58,6±0,8	92,8±0,6
The width of the interval between the iliac crests	23,6±0,2	43,8±0,4	24,4±0,4	45,5±0,6
Chest width	34,5±0,3	68,4±0,9	36,4±0,5	71,4±0,4
Slant length of body	124,1±0,1	151,6±0,5	128,3±0,2	156,9±0,8
Chest circumference	157,2±0,2	242,8±0,2	160,9±0,1	250,1±0,9
Pocha circle	16,3±0,9	35,1±0,2	18,2±0,9	37,3±0,3

The analysis of this table showed that the bulls of experimental group II had priority over their peers in all periods of growth.

Fig. 1. (Measurement of cattle in the experimental group)

Based on the body measurements of the animals in the experimental group, we determined their body composition indices and listed them in Table 2 below.

Table 2.

Body composition indices of animals in experimental groups,%

Name of indexes	Groups			
	I		II	
	Age in months			
	6	18	6	18
Long-leggedness	47,1	37,6	46,1	36,4
Elongation	121,3	107,1	117,5	107,4

Chestiness	63,7	77,4	62,2	76,9
Pelvis-chest	146,1	156,1	149,1	156,9
Density	126,6	160,1	125,4	159,4
Growth	101,7	100,7	103,0	101,4
Bony	15,9	24,8	16,6	25,5

From the data in Table 2, it can be concluded that the animals in the experimental groups differ from each other in terms of long-leggedness and density index in the first months of life. As they age, all animals in the experiment resemble the exterior of mature animals.

Breast size and pelvic-chest indices decreased with age. An intergroup difference was observed for the ossification index, which characterizes the development of bone tissue.

Summary. The results obtained in our research show that regardless of the sex and age of the animals, the body structure index of dairy and co-producing animals is high, which indicates the rapid growth of muscle and bone tissue and high meat productivity.

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